

Original article

Antibiotics prescription patterns and barriers to antimicrobial stewardship among physicians at a tertiary hospital in North-eastern Nigeria

Attahiru Muhammad,^{1*} Muhammad D. Haruna,^{1,2} Sani M Kabir,¹ Yakubu B Abdul-Rasheed,¹ Zakari I. Wase,¹ Pitmang S. Lambo,¹ Dalhat I. Sulaiman,¹ Faiza M. Dahiru,¹ Asmau U Bello,¹ Grema A .Bukar.³

¹Department of Family Medicine Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital Bauchi, Nigeria

²Department of Family Medicine Federal University of Health Science Azare, Bauchi, Nigeria

³Department of Family Medicine Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital, Kano, Nigeria)

Corresponding author: Dr Attahiru Muhammad, Department of Family Medicine Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital Bauchi, Nigeria. Email:attamoh2go@yahoo.com Tel No.+234-8035077012

Abstract

Background: Global action plans to tackle antimicrobial resistance (AMR) include implementing antimicrobial stewardship (AMS), but few studies have directly addressed the challenges faced by low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). **Objective:** This study aimed to assess antibiotics prescription patterns and barriers to antimicrobial stewardship (AMS) among physicians in Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital, Bauchi, North-eastern Nigeria. **Materials and methods:** This cross-sectional study was conducted among 133 physicians (response rate of 80.6%) practising at Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital, Bauchi. Participants were asked to complete an electronic survey after meeting them at their working sites. A structured self-administered questionnaire was used to collect data via convenience sampling. Frequency and percentages were used to summarise data. Bivariate analysis (Chi-square test) was used to assess associations, with statistical significance set at $P < 0.05$. **Result:** The mean age of the physicians was 35.9 ± 6.5 years with a male preponderance of 71%. The majority of physicians (88.7%) believed they had a higher average rate of antibiotic prescriptions than their peers in the same clinical speciality. More than half 51.1% have a good composite self-perceived knowledge of AMS. The major barriers against the AMS implementation were a lack of funding, lack of sufficient healthcare providers, and a shortage of AMS team members. The least-ranked barrier was the lack of awareness among hospital administration of AMS. **Conclusion:** In general, the study participants had a relatively good self-perceived knowledge but reported insufficient implementation of AMS programs. The main barriers to AMS implementation were a lack of funding, a shortage of healthcare providers, and a shortage of AMS team members.

Keywords: Antibiotics, Antimicrobial, Bauchi, North-east, Stewardship.

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Introduction

The emergence and spread of antibiotic resistance have been a major issue for both public health and the world economy since the 1940s.¹ It has become a widespread issue that can lead to infections that are very difficult to treat and often require costly and toxic drugs.² One of the reasons why it is becoming a global issue is due to the constant use of antimicrobial products, as well as overprescribing antibiotics.² About 30% of unnecessary oral antibiotics are prescribed in health care facilities.¹ Most of these prescriptions are issued for non-bacterial infections, particularly acute respiratory conditions such as asthma, allergic disorders, and the common cold.

To curtail this menace, many health professionals including doctors, pharmacy and other health practitioners, in addition to health organizations, have collaborated to form and implement the antimicrobial stewardship (AMS) program which is a set of synchronized interventions that optimize anti-bacterial use to generate the best clinical outcome, increase patient safety, and reduce the risk of antimicrobial resistance development.³ As primary prescribers of antimicrobials, physicians are integral to AMS implementation through their influence on medicine-use practices and patient management decisions. However, it is widely recognised that AMS programmes are more challenging to implement in low- and middle-income countries. These challenges are multifactorial and include shortages of skilled AMS personnel, limited training and educational opportunities, inadequate pharmacy resources, insufficient engagement from private practice physicians, and low prioritisation amid competing healthcare demands.⁴ A qualitative assessment of knowledge, perception and experience of physicians about antimicrobial stewardship in Nigeria during the COVID-19 pandemic showed that 83% of the respondents think auditing clinicians would promote antibiotic stewardship, 44% were unaware of clinical guidelines for an empirical antibiotics prescription.⁵ The critical role of antimicrobial stewardship in mitigating antimicrobial resistance cannot be overemphasised. However, there is a need to assess physicians' knowledge, awareness and perceptions about AMS in Nigeria to enhance the practice of responsible prescription of antibiotics. Therefore, this study aimed to explore physicians' antibiotic prescribing patterns, their knowledge and perceptions of AMS, and their perceived barriers to the development and implementation of AMS in hospitals, with a view to informing strategies for the appropriate use of antimicrobial agents in human health, animal health, and food systems.

Materials and Methods

A descriptive cross-sectional study employing quantitative methods was undertaken among physicians practicing at Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital, Bauchi, as they are the key health professionals directly involved in prescribing antimicrobials in the hospitals. The

hospital is a seven hundred-bed space capacity tertiary health facility accredited for postgraduate training in medical sciences, among other mandates are research and services.

During the study period, all eligible physicians present during departmental meetings within the study period were invited to participate. Thus, although recruitment was opportunity-based, efforts were made to include physicians across all major clinical departments (Surgery, Paediatrics, Family Medicine, Haematology-Oncology, Emergency Medicine, Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Internal Medicine, and other physicians involved directly in antibiotic prescribing). A minimum sample size of 166 was calculated using Yamane's formula based on the total physician population ($N = 242$) at a 5% margin of error.⁶ However, due to logistical constraints, participant recruitment was conducted using a non-probability (convenience) sampling approach.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N * (e)^2}$$

Where:

n = the sample size

N = the total population of physicians at Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital Bauchi, stood at 242 at the time of the study

e = the margin of error in the calculation which is usually set at 5%

$$n = 242 \div [1 + 242(0.05)^2] = 242 \div 1.605$$

$$n = 150.8$$

To compensate for incompletely filled questionnaires or incomplete responses, the final sample size formula, effective sample size divided by one minus the anticipated non-response rate (10%) was used.

Final sample size (n_f) = Effective sample size / 1 - non-response rate anticipated (10%)

$$n_f = 151 / 1 - 0.1$$

$$n_f = 166$$

The final sample size was 166

We included physicians (graduate, postgraduate, and consultant doctors) practising in the specified departments at the time of data collection, as well as the clinical heads of these departments. The study excluded other health care providers that were not medical practitioners and physicians and clinical heads in other departments not mentioned. Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the health research Ethics Committee (HREC) of the Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital, Bauchi. The study was conducted in accordance with the Helsinki Declaration, which was revised in 2013.

Formal permission to collect data was obtained from the hospital management at each respective site. Written informed consent was obtained from each participant before enrolment in the study. Completion of the questionnaires was anonymous, and data were maintained.

A structured, self-administered questionnaire was used to collect data on the following aspects: (i) participants' socio-demographic characteristics; (ii) physicians' antibiotic prescribing patterns; (iii) knowledge of antimicrobial stewardship (AMS) practices; (iv) factors supporting effective AMS programmes; and (v) barriers to delivering a functional and effective AMS programme. The questionnaire was adapted from previously validated instruments used in a similar study assessing antimicrobial stewardship practices.⁷ Minor contextual modifications were made to suit the local setting. It was initially piloted among fifteen (15) physicians at the State Specialist Hospital in Bauchi to assess consistency, length, and relevance of the questions. Necessary adjustments were made prior to administering the final, updated questionnaires to the respondents.

The collected data were checked for completeness and accuracy before analysis. Incomplete questionnaires were excluded and counted as non-responses. All complete questionnaires were entered into Microsoft Excel and exported to the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), Version 25.

Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were used to characterise the variables of interest. Antibiotic prescribing patterns and AMS perceived knowledge were assessed using proportions. A composite self-perceived AMS competence score was constructed by assigning numerical values (excellent = 4, very good = 3, good = 2, fair = 1) to two Likert-scale items (perceived awareness/knowledge of empirical antibiotic prescribing guidelines and their self-reported use of such guidelines in clinical practice). Scores were summed (range 2-8) and dichotomised at the median, with scores ≤ 4 as poor and scores above 4 as good self-perceived knowledge. This variable represents self-perceived competence and not objective knowledge. Likert scores for factors supporting effective AMS programmes were grouped as follows: 1 = Yes, 2 = No, and 3 = Not sure. In contrast, responses regarding barriers to delivering a functional and effective AMS

programme were reclassified as 'agree' (strongly agree/agree), 'disagree' (strongly disagree/disagree), and 'neutral'. The Pearson chi-square test was used to determine the significance of associations between physicians' perceived AMS knowledge and categorical variables. Binary logistic regression was used to assess relationships between independent variables with outcome variables. Statistical significance was set at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results

Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents

A total of 135 questionnaires were returned out of 165 distributed, giving a response rate of approximately 80.6%. Two questionnaires were incomplete; consequently only 133 were analysed and had their findings reported. The mean age of respondents was 35.9 ± 6.5 years, with an age range of 24 -55 years.

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics of respondents (N=133)

Variables	Freq	Per cent (%)	Mean \pm SD (Range)
Age (years)			35.9 \pm 6.5 (24 - 55)
Gender distribution			
Male	94	70.7	
Female	39	29.3	
Cadre of Physician			
House Officer	23	17.3	
Medical Officer	19	14.3	
Junior Resident	42	31.6	
Senior Resident	21	15.8	
Consultant	28	21.1	
Physicians' specialty			
Internal Medicine	19	14.3	
Surgery	15	11.3	
Pediatrics	17	12.3	
Obstetrics and Gynaecology	18	13.5	
Accident and Emergency	4	3.0	
Family Medicine	25	18.8	
Others	35	26.3	
Duration of practice (years)			
< 1	18	13.5	
1-5	34	25.6	
>5	81	60.1	
Duration in current speciality (years)			
< 1	21	15.8	
1-5	72	54.1	
>5	40	29.1	

^aTest proportion (binomial)

More than two-thirds (94; 70.7%) were male. The majority of physicians (81; 60.1%) had been in practice for more than 5 years, while slightly more than half (72; 54.1%) had spent 1-5 years in their current speciality.

Prescription Pattern of Antibiotic among Physicians Table 2 shows that the average number of patients who were prescribed at least one antibiotic per week was 2.12 ± 1.51 . More than two-thirds of physicians (98; 73.7%) believed they had a similar average rate of antibiotic prescriptions compared to their peers in the same clinical specialty. More than three-quarters (106; 79.7%) indicated that they prescribe both generic and branded products interchangeably, whilst only (24; 18.0%) prescribed generic products exclusively and (3; 2.3%) prescribed branded products exclusively. Among the factors that determine antibiotic prescription, clinical judgment without laboratory result (70%), cost to patients (65.4%) and drug availability (57.6%) were the major determinants. Close to half of the physicians, 40.6%, claimed to have good knowledge and use of guidelines for prescribing empirical antibiotics, with the majority, 83.5%, believing that auditing clinicians would promote antibiotic stewardship. However, 45.9% felt that doctors were not provided thorough training on antibiotic stewardship. More than half (51.1%) have a good composite self-perceived knowledge of AMS.

Knowledge of Antimicrobial Stewardship Practice in Hospital Settings

In the bivariable analysis, AMS self-perceived knowledge among physicians was significantly associated with the physician specialty ($p = 0.004$) and years of practice ($p = 0.048$). After controlling confounders, the multivariable logistic regression model showed that only physicians practising in surgical specialties (AOR: 4.34, $p = 0.018$) were

significantly more likely to have relatively good self-perceived AMS knowledge than their counterparts in the medical specialties (See table 4). Close to half of the physicians, 40.6%, claimed to have good knowledge and use of guidelines for prescribing empirical antibiotics, with the majority, 83.5%, believing that auditing clinicians would promote antibiotic stewardship. However, 45.9% felt that doctors were not provided thorough training on antibiotic stewardship. More than half (51.1%) have a good composite self-perceived knowledge of AMS.

Table 2: Prescription Pattern of Antibiotics Among Physicians

Variables	Freq	Per cent (%)
Mean prescribed antibiotic/week = 2.12 ± 1.51		
Antibiotic Prescriptions Rate		
high	20	15.0
Average	98	73.7
low	15	11.3
Form of Antibiotic Prescribed		
generic and branded	106	79.7
generic only	24	18.0
branded only	3	2.3
Factors that Determine Antibiotic Prescription		
drug promotional and marketing influences	41	30.8
clinical judgment (without laboratory result)	94	70.7
laboratory results	70	52.6
experience	66	49.6
cost to patients	87	65.4
drug availability	76	57.1
epidemiology of infection	51	38.3
best evidence (literature)	59	44.3
senior colleague's decision	39	29.3
unit policy	44	33.1
hospital policy (treatment guideline)	40	30.1

Table 3: Knowledge of Antimicrobial Stewardship Practice in Hospital Settings

Variables	Freq	(%)
Do you think auditing clinicians would promote antibiotic stewardship?		
yes	111	83.5
no	8	6.0
maybe	14	10.5
How would you describe your awareness, knowledge and use of guidelines for empirical antibiotic prescriptions?		
excellent	14	10.5
very good	48	36.1
good	54	40.6
fair	17	12.8
In your own practice, how would you describe your use of guidelines for prescribing antibiotics for your patients?		
excellent	11	8.3
very good	52	39.1
good	50	37.6
fair	20	15.0
Do you think doctors have thorough training (both in medical school and internship) about antibiotic stewardship?		
yes	72	54.1
no	61	45.9
Perceived Knowledge of Antibiotic Stewardship		
Good	68	51.1
Poor	65	48.9

Table 4: Factors that Support Effective Implementation of AMS among Physicians

	Physicians' Self-perceived Knowledge on Antimicrobial Stewardship					
	Good (n =68)	Poor (n =65)	χ^2	P-value	AOR (95% CI)	P-value
	n (%)	n (%)				
Age (years)						
20-30	17(13)	13(10)	1.928	0.381	1	0.680
31-40	36(27)	42(32)			2.1 (0.41-10.30)	0.380
>40	15(11)	10(8)			1.4 (0.47-4.06)	0.563
Gender						
Female	16(12)	23(17)	2.254	0.133	1	
Male	52(39)	42(32)			1.6 (0.67- 3.66)	0.303
Medical Cadre						
Senior	25(19)	23(17)	0.027	0.868	1	
Junior	43(32)	42(32)			0.75 (0.28-2.00)	0.563
Specialty						
Medical	27(20)	38(29)	11.042	0.004*	1	0.061
Surgical	19(14)	21(16)			4.34 (1.29-14.66)	0.018*
Others	22(17)	6(5)			3.46 (0.96-12.45)	0.057
Duration of practice (years)						
< 1	14(11)	4(3)	6.073	0.048*	1	0.425
1-5	15(11)	19(14)			0.32 (0.06-1.83)	0.202
>5	39(29)	42(32)			0.85 (0.30-2.40)	0.754

COR: Crude Odds Ratio, AOR: Adjusted Odds Ratio, CI: Confidence Interval * indicate significant difference at $p < 0.05$.

Figure 1: Barriers to Delivering a Functional and Effective Antimicrobial Stewardship

Figure 1 shows physicians' perceptions of the barriers to delivering a functional and effective AMS. The results indicate that the main barrier to AMS implementation was lack of funding (79.7%), followed by insufficient healthcare providers (75.0%), and a shortage of AMS team members (73.7%). The least frequently reported barrier was lack of awareness of AMS among hospital administrators (28.6%).

Discussion

Appropriate drug utilization contributes immensely to a global reduction in morbidity and mortality as a result of its medical, social, and economic benefits. Positive effects of antimicrobial stewardship interventions in low- and middle-income countries have been previously reported. Using the WHO prescribing indicators, this study provided a better understanding of prescribing practices in the healthcare facility and highlighted areas needing intervention. The findings indicated overprescribing of antibiotics, as measured by the average number of patients receiving at least one antibiotic per week (2.12 ± 1.51), with more than two-thirds of physicians (74%) believing that their rate of antibiotic prescriptions was similar to or higher than that of their peers in the same clinical specialty. This is similar to the findings of two recent point prevalence studies in Nigeria by Oduyebo et al.⁸ and Umeokonkwo et al.⁹ which reported rates of 69.7% and 78.2%, respectively. This is much higher than the ideal value

recommended by WHO of <30%.¹⁰ The perceived high frequency of antimicrobial prescriptions among physicians in this study may be attributable to several factors, including the practice of prescribing antibiotics without culture and sensitivity testing, reliance on symptomatic or empirical treatment, inadequate adherence to available country-specific treatment guidelines, and limited knowledge or clinical experience of the prescribers.¹¹

Prescribing drugs using their generic names is an important aspect of rational drug use, as it helps to minimise undesirable drug interactions, adverse drug reactions, and medication errors.¹² This study showed that more than three-quarters of physicians (80%) reported prescribing both generic and branded products interchangeably, while only 18% prescribed generic products exclusively. This contrasts with the WHO-based drug-prescribing patterns observed in four hospitals in southern Ethiopia, where an average of 95.8% of drugs were prescribed by their generic names.¹² This suggests that health professionals in this facility continue to prescribe using brand names, which is consistent with findings from studies conducted in Nigeria and India.^{13,14}

Among the factors determining antibiotic prescription in this study, clinical judgement without laboratory results, cost to patients, and drug availability were the major determinants. A similar study of physicians in a tertiary hospital in Lagos, Nigeria, reported that cost, drug availability, and pressure from pharmaceutical representatives

were the primary drivers of irrational antibiotic prescribing among participants.¹⁵ Contrastingly, a cross-sectional study in Saudi Arabia found that the most frequently reported factors influencing antibiotic prescribing decisions were advice from a specialist, guidance from a senior colleague, previous experience or training, and the use of local or national guidelines/protocols.⁵

This study found that more than half 51.1% have a relatively good composite self-perceived AMS competence. They also indicated that doctors were not provided with thorough training in antibiotic stewardship. This is similar to a descriptive, cross-sectional study in Zambia involving 137 physicians and 61 pharmacists, which found that AMS knowledge was relatively low among physicians (51%) and pharmacists (39%), and that most physicians (92%) and pharmacists (86%) had not previously undertaken AMS training. A comparable study assessing the prescribing practices, knowledge, and attitudes of Nigerian physicians in leading tertiary hospitals reported that physicians' knowledge of AMS and their core components was relatively low, with only 36.5% demonstrating good knowledge.¹⁶

This study showed that AMS knowledge among physicians was significantly associated with physician years of practice ($p = 0.048$). This finding is consistent with previous reports, which indicated that knowledge levels were significantly associated with practitioners' years of professional experience, position or practice rank, and prior AMS training.^{16,17} The low AMS knowledge scores of practitioners with less duration of practice could affect the implementation of AMS programs in terms of comprehensiveness, quality, and adoption to lower community health facilities. These findings highlight the need for structured AMS training tailored to junior cadre physicians in Nigeria, including integration into undergraduate curricula, mandatory internship-level orientation, and regular hospital-based CME programmes. Strengthening multidisciplinary AMS committees within tertiary hospitals may further support early-career physicians and enhance stewardship implementation.¹⁸

The logistic regression model showed that physicians practicing in surgical specialties (AOR: 4.34, 95% CI: 1.29–14.66) were significantly more likely to have higher self-perceived AMS knowledge scores compared to those in medical specialties. Specialty-related differences have also been reported in a national survey conducted in the United States.¹⁹ In that study, participant responses varied according to specialty; for example,

pediatricians demonstrated greater awareness of antibiotic resistance at the national level but were less likely to perceive inappropriate prescribing as a problem in their own practice.¹⁹ Together, these findings suggest that perceptions and awareness of antimicrobial stewardship may vary across specialties, although the specific patterns differ between settings

The results of this study indicated that the main barrier to AMS implementation was lack of funding (79.7%), followed by insufficient healthcare providers (75.0%), and a shortage of AMS team members (73.7%). The least frequently reported barrier was lack of awareness of AMS among hospital administrators (28.6%). A study by Iregbu et al. in Nigeria identified several challenges impeding AMS activities, including lack of human and financial resources, prescribers' opposition, absence of AMS committees, and limited awareness.²⁰ Other commonly reported barriers include disintegration of teams, poor communication, shortage of AMS team members, insufficient education and training, and inadequate health information technology.^{21,22}

This study has several limitations. It was conducted in a single tertiary hospital and included only a subset of healthcare professionals in Bauchi State, which limits generalisability to other institutions and the wider health workforce. The achieved sample size ($n = 133$) was lower than the planned target ($n = 166$), which may have reduced statistical precision and power. Some adjusted associations, such as age 31–40 years (AOR = 2.1, 95% CI: 0.41–10.30), had wide confidence intervals, reflecting imprecision due to the modest sample size and limited events in certain subgroups. In addition, convenience sampling was employed, which may limit the representativeness of the findings. Finally, the findings may not fully reflect practices in all healthcare settings beyond the study site.

In general, the study participants had a relatively good level of knowledge but reported the insufficient implementation of AMS programs. The main barrier to AMS implementation was lack of funding, followed by Lack of sufficient healthcare providers, and shortage of AMS team members. The result of this study may draw the attention of policymakers to the importance of AMS and the barriers to its' implementation, which could positively reflect on the effective implementation of AMS at their institution.

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